

Master in Sound and Music Computing
Universitat Pompeu Fabra

Exploring the impact of musical feedback systems on physical endurance

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Supervisor: Rafael Ramírez-Meléndez

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Dedication

I would like to dedicate this work to my parents, to my friends and to Inés, for their endless support, love and encouragement.

Acknowledgement

I would like to express my sincere gratitude to:

- My supervisor, Rafael Ramírez-Meléndez, for his guidance during the development of this project.
- My classmates, acquaintances and friends who were kind enough to participate in the tests, for making this study possible.

Abstract

Music has been proven to have an ergogenic effect in the context of physical activity. It can reduce one's perceived level of exertion by mitigating the negative feelings caused by the struggle associated with exercise. However, several studies have shown that these benefits can be amplified by inducing a state of musical agency. Musical agency aims to make the user an active participant in the musical output rather than a passive listener. This can be achieved by implementing what is known as a musical feedback system (MFS). For this project, three different MFS were developed in the form of Android apps, each of which empowers the user by giving them control over their workout music in a unique way.

The first musical feedback system consists of music loops that become increasingly more intense and complex as the fluctuation of the accelerometer values grows. Four instruments play simultaneously on different tracks, with three of them being mapped to a different axis plus percussion being mapped to the average fluctuation of all axes. The variation of accelerometer values is measured both on a long term and short term basis.

The second application that was developed counts movement repetitions by detecting significant sign changes on any axis of the accelerometer values. It sets a target of repetitions within a time window, and depending on the user's performance, different audio effect parameters are tweaked. The user can select any song or audio clip to play while exercising, and at first very aggressive distortion and a restrictive low-pass filter will be applied. As their performance improves, the audio effects become less intrusive.

The third musical feedback system allows the user to specify up to 5 different positions, which will be used to train a custom K-NN algorithm. Subsequently, each of them is assigned a different audio clip, which is triggered every time the K-NN classification algorithm detects a change in the current smartphone orientation. Different instruments are available and can be selected through the user interface.

Lastly, cooperative versions of the first and second musical feedback systems were also developed. These use a PC as a host, and accelerometer values are sent via OSC protocol. In the cooperative loop-based application, each of the four instruments is assigned to a different participant, with loop intensity being mapped to the overall fluctuation of accelerometer data. In the cooperative version of the repetition counter, two participants are each assigned a different audio effect (distortion and low-pass filter), which they must mitigate by performing exercises at the expected pace.

An experiment was conducted to test the second application (Audio effect modulation through a movement counter). The physical endurance of 9 different participants was tested under two different conditions: passive listening and musical agency. A quantitative and qualitative data analysis was performed. Results seem to point toward an increase in physical endurance and enjoyment when subjects use the musical feedback system.

Keywords: musical feedback system; musical agency; physical endurance; exercise.

Chapter 1

Introduction

This study aims to explore the benefits that musical agency can provide in the exercise domain. In this context, we employ the definition of musical agency proposed by Thomas H. Fritz: bodily movement guided by an agent, and governed by the goal of modulating musical sounds [1]. This is, essentially, the feeling of playing a musical instrument, an experience in which our movement controls a musical output.

In order for the movements of a workout session to be converted into a music making experience, there is a need to design a device that will map motion data to a variety of musical parameters. This is what is known as a musical feedback system, which in this analogy acts as the musical instrument itself.

Several musical feedback systems have been developed over the past decade, many of them with a focus on enhancing the workout experience, but also others with therapeutic objectives. However, a common drawback of most of these systems is that they require specific motion sensors, and sometimes use proprietary technologies. As a result, many of these systems, which have been proven to be deeply beneficial, are unfortunately not very accessible.

For this reason, it was decided that the musical feedback systems developed for this project should require no specialized hardware. Instead, the motion sensors present in smartphones would serve as the sole input pathway and all of the necessary

processing would be done through software.

1.1 Motivation

The motivation behind this Master's thesis stems from the many benefits that musical feedback systems have been proven to bring in terms of well-being and workout performance. Nonetheless, up until this point they have generally been outside of reach to the general public, with many of them using proprietary sensors, specific exercise machines or being closed source software. Moreover, in most cases users do not have a choice when it comes to the music that musical feedback systems produce, leading to biases related to each individual's personal music taste.

The project is born out of the necessity to create a musical feedback system that is accessible, versatile and customizable, while hopefully retaining all of the benefits that musical agency is known to bring. By doing so, a wider range of users might be able to experience the increase in physical endurance and enjoyment that has been reported across different studies regarding musical feedback systems.

Furthermore, even though it is not a main objective in this specific study, musical feedback systems have also been applied in the context of music therapy. By creating a customizable software application and publishing it as an open source project, it allows for future researchers and therapists to adapt the app to their needs in fields other than exercise.

On a more personal note, I have previously worked on a therapeutic video game aimed at children diagnosed with Central Auditory Processing Disorder. The project aimed to bring some variety and joy to the otherwise repetitive training exercises they had to practice. In that sense, this Master's thesis shares certain similarities with my previous project. My hope is that this project will serve as a small contribution in what I consider to be a fascinating field, as we strive to develop better musical interactive systems that can improve our performance, endurance and enjoyment of the exercise experience.

1.2 Objectives

The methodology of this master's thesis can be divided into two parts. The first part consists of the development of a musical feedback system through iterative prototyping. The second half focuses on the testing of said system and the subsequent data analysis. With this in mind, the main objectives of this project are as follows:

- To develop a musical feedback system that is accessible, by leveraging the in-built motion sensors present in widely available devices, such as smartphones.
- To maximize the longevity of the system and minimize the bias caused by music taste preferences by allowing users to choose whichever song they favor.
- To test the effects of said system when it comes to the perceived level of exhaustion, the physical endurance and the enjoyment felt by users.

Having established the objectives for this Master's thesis, three main research questions were formulated:

- Is it possible to build a musical feedback system based solely on off-the-shelf sensors such as the ones included in an average smartphone?
- Can such a musical feedback system increase physical endurance by inducing a state of musical agency?
- Does this state of musical agency result in an increase in workout performance while maintaining a similar level of exertion?

As the literature review in chapter 2 shows, not many musical feedback systems have been developed by relying solely on smartphone motion sensors. However, there exists one relevant example in the portable version of D-Jogger [2], a software application which continuously adjusts the music that is playing in order to synchronise it to the walking cadence of the user. Therefore, the hypothesis in regards

to the first research question is that it is possible to develop a functioning system under such constraints.

Concerning the second and third research questions, a hypothesis can also be formulated by considering previous studies in the field. Based on the research done by Fritz et. al. [3] and Rehfeld et. al. [4] the hypothesis is that, if the musical feedback system is effectively able to induce a state of musical agency, results should indeed show an increase in workout performance while maintaining a similar level of exertion.

1.3 Structure of the Report

This report is divided into five chapters. Following this brief introduction, chapter 2 delves into the State Of The Art. Some relevant studies relating to the health benefits of music, physical activity and the combination of both will be outlined in this section. A variety of studies related to musical feedback systems will also be examined. Next, in chapter 3, the materials and methods used during this project will be discussed. The section on materials will list all relevant hardware, software and additional elements that made this study possible. On the other hand, methodology will be focusing on both the implementation of several musical feedback systems and the tests conducted to evaluate their effects.

Chapter 4 will show the results of the previously mentioned tests, both from a quantitative and a usability standpoint. A series of graphs and tables will aid the visualization of the outcome. Finally, chapter 5 will include the discussion and conclusions acquired from the results. The whole project will be put into perspective mentioning limitations and future work, but also highlighting the possible benefits of systems such as these.

Chapter 2

State Of The Art

In this chapter, the scientific and technical background which served as a basis for this project will be presented and discussed. First, the general health benefits of music and exercise will be examined. Secondly, specific examples of musical feedback systems will be shown, discussing both their benefits and design philosophy.

2.1 Health benefits of music listening

According to a study by M. L. Chanda and D. J. Levitin, music can be incredibly powerful from a neurochemical standpoint. Listening to music can stimulate the release of dopamine, a hormone that is related to reward, motivation and pleasure. Furthermore, engaging in group activities related to rhythm, such as dancing, can result in an increased levels of oxytocin, a hormone that regulates social behaviour [5].

A review by Fancourt et. al. outlines how music has also been used in the context of therapy as a non-intrusive way to reduce stress. Listening to music leads to brainstem responses that regulate heart rate, pulse, blood pressure, body temperature, skin conductance, and muscle tension. Many studies have shown that it can also reduce cortisol levels, a hormone associated with stress, although musical taste seems to be an important variable in this regard [6].

In fact, over the past couple of decades music therapy has been a growing field, as its effects when combined with standard care seem quite significant. For example, a meta-analysis and review of 15 different studies in which music was used to aid the treatment of patients diagnosed with schizophrenia and depression, concluded that it improved their global state, symptoms, and functioning capabilities. They reach a similar consensus to the previous cited study, claiming that it serves as a motivating tool, a medium for emotional expression, and a social activity [7].

2.2 Health benefits of exercise

Exercising often is an extremely powerful indicator of someone's general well-being. G. N. Rueggeggerand and F. W. Booth concluded that at least 40 different common conditions can worsen due to a lack of physical activity [8]. These range from general afflictions such as biological aging or pain to specific conditions such as type 2 diabetes, strokes or several forms of cancer. Moreover, exercising is the best way to improve cardio-respiratory fitness, which might be the best way to lower mortality risk.

Regular physical activity has also shown to have an extraordinarily positive effect on mental health. Just like music, it can be used as a non-invasive form of therapy to facilitate improvements in nueroplasticity and cognition [9] as well as depression [10] and anxiety [11]. It has also been proven to aid the prevention and treatment of neurodegenerative diseases, such as Parkinson's [12] and Alzheimer's disease [13], as well as substance use disorders [14].

2.3 Music and exercise

Listening to music while exercising has been proven to be immensely beneficial. Karageorghis and Priest wrote a two-part review and synthesis of the most relevant scientific papers related to music in the exercise domain [15, 16]. The consensus that has been reached is that the main role of music in exercise is to minimize the perceived sense of exertion while having an ergogenic effect. In essence, music allows

people to accomplish more and simultaneously reduces negative feelings associated with greater effort. The performance-enhancing capabilities of music when used for synchronous movement are related to the established tendency of the human body to react physically to the rhythmic elements of music.

A study by MacDougall and Moore showed that 2 Hz (which is equivalent to 120 BPM) seems to be a common movement frequency when analysing human locomotion [17]. For example, it is a common walking frequency, and when humans are asked to tap their fingers to a beat, 120 BPM seems exceptionally widespread [18]. The authors believed that this could reflect the tempo of a spinal central pattern generator. This system, previously only found in animals, could explain locomotor rhythmicity. This ties in with the fact that the 120 BPM tempo is so common in modern Western music[19].

Schneider et. al. built upon MacDougall and Moore's study in an attempt to find a 3 Hz intrinsic locomotive frequency in the context of running [20]. They found a strong connection between vertical body oscillation during running, heart rate, electroencephalographic delta activity, and peak power output with the participants' preferred running music. This music, chosen by participants themselves, seemed to have its most dominant frequencies in the range of 2.6 Hz - 2.8 Hz (for frequencies below 5 Hz), suggesting that in the context of running, faster tempos are preferred. In fact, a study by Meaghan et. al. found that cycling with fast tempo music (130 BPM) elicited an increase in breathing and heart rate frequency, as well as exercise duration, while not influencing the rate of perceived exertion [21].

2.4 Musical Feedback Systems

This section of the literature review takes a look at a variety of musical feedback systems that have been developed over the last decade. In this context, a musical feedback system could be defined as an interface which receives input from motion sensors and maps their data to a variety of musical parameters. As a result, a feeling of musical agency may be awakened, which could be described as actively

and purposefully controlling musical sounds through bodily movement.

2.4.1 Jymmin

Several studies led by Thomas H. Fritz have shown that the benefits of listening to music while exercising can be enhanced by making the user an active participant instead of a passive listener [1]. This is what he calls "a state of musical agency", which can be reached by implementing musical feedback systems in workout routines. A considerable part of Fritz's research revolves around Jymmin, a musical feedback system developed to explore the potential benefits of musical agency in the context of exercise.

The original Jymmin system consisted of three exercise machines: a pulldown machine, a stepper, and an abdominal exercise machine with handles. Each of these machines had sensors installed which could detect even small movements by the users. These movements were mapped to different audio effects in the digital audio workstation Ableton Live 8, such as band filters and pitch shifts. As a result, the user would have control over the parameters of these effects, and therefore the musical piece as a whole, which consisted of different loops of electronic dance music.

There are many potential benefits to implementing a musical feedback system like Jymmin in workout routines. One study indicated that participants perceived a lower sense of exertion and required lower amounts of oxygen consumption when exercising [3]. This happened despite the fact that they were applying comparable amounts of force as the control group, which was only passively listening to music. Authors attribute this difference in metabolism to the fact that the musical agency state can provide greater relaxation, thereby reducing muscle tension.

A different study focused on the emotional disposition of participants after partaking in a musical feedback workout session [1]. Participants took the Multidimensional Mood Questionnaire after exercising under two different conditions (passive listening and musical agency). The results of said questionnaire show participants had a more positive mindset after experiencing physical activity in a musical agency state. This

could be related to an increase in hormone levels, more specifically endorphins.

The Jymmin musical feedback system has been extensively tested in different contexts, with positive results overall. On one occasion, tests were conducted with a group of elderly people who did not regularly exercise, installing the sensors on a Spider Body exercise machine. Results indicated longer sets and better pacing [4]. Another study focused on the potential benefits of musical agency in terms of creativity. Subjects were divided into three groups: the first one would engage in musical activities without exercising, the second one would be exercising while passively listening to music, and the third one would exercise with the musical feedback system. The third group vastly outperformed the others in the Guilford Alternative Uses task [22].

The system has also been tested as a sort of musical therapy in a rehabilitation setting. The first instance of this use case focused on a group of polydrug abusers [23]. After a musical feedback intervention, participants listened to the music piece they had arranged during their workout. This had positive effects on their confidence, mood, and willingness to engage socially. Despite perceiving a “high”, presumably from the increased endorphin release, users did not report a desire for the consumption of substances. In fact, 67% of participants alleged that the musical euphoria they experienced could serve as an alternative to intoxication by drugs [24].

A more recent study by Lydia Schneider et. al. conducted an experiment explore the benefits of Jymmin in regard to the anxiety levels of a group of patients in chronic pain [25]. Physical activity is highly beneficial for most chronic pain patients, but due to the anticipation of pain it is often avoided. Results showed that patients who exercised using Jymmin had significantly lower anxiety levels than those who didn't, probably due to a reduced amount of tension in the antagonist muscle.

2.4.2 Sound Control

Another relevant project in the field of sensor-based interactive music systems is Sound Control [26], developed by Samuel Thompson et. al. Sound Control is a

platform for creating Digital Musical Instruments aimed at children with diverse disabilities. It can be configured to recognize inputs from a variety of sensors. Some of them are quite common, such as webcam-based color detection, microphone audio or mouse tracking, making it accessible to most people without the need for specialized hardware. However, it also allows the user to connect more specific sensors such as LeapMotion (which tracks palms gestures), BBC micro:bit (a programmable device with a variety of sensors) and GameTrak (a controller which detects 3D positioning of hands by pulling two strings from a base).

In terms of the mapping of the sensors, Interactive Machine Learning (IML) was used in order to quickly and easily adapt the Digital Musical Instrument to the child's needs. For example, different patients may have distinct motion ranges and patterns. Depending on the mode used, sound will be mapped using k-nearest neighbors (for classification tasks), a multilayer perceptron neural network (for regression tasks), or a combination of both. There are two training options: "Quick", which randomly maps different outputs to different positions assumed by the user during one continuous movement; and "Precise", in which each position is mapped individually with the current sound as the target.

Sound Control includes a total of six of different music and sound modes: Sample Player, Looper, MIDI Mapper, Granulator, Mixer and FMSynth. The first three (Sample Player, Looper and MIDI Mapper) use k-NN classification to map the sensor's readings to specific audio clips or MIDI notes. Granulator, Mixer and FMSynth add neural networks to the equation in order to smoothly control different parameters of the audio samples (such as pitch or volume), or synthesis, in the case of FMSynth.

2.4.3 moBeat

In 2011, Van Der Vlist et. al. created moBeat, which allows the user to interact with music by cycling on a stationary bicycle [27]. This system uses speed and cadence sensors, which are attached to the rear wheel of the bike, as well as a heart rate belt that the user must wear. The sensors' readings are then processed in Max/MSP,

adjusting the tempo and musical richness of the MIDI notes generated by a MIDI sequencer in the Digital Audio Workstation Logic Pro 8.

In this study, moBeat was tested against a reference system, with participants having to complete an Intrinsic Motivation Inventory (IMI) and Attentional Focus Questionnaire (AFQ). MoBeat scored higher in terms of enjoyment, perceived competence and usefulness, while scoring lower in terms of distress and dissociation. In terms of perceived exertion, no significant difference was found when compared to the reference system. These results are consistent with those related to Jymmin.

2.4.4 PedaleoVR

A more recent study by P. Kantan and A. Rojo et al. combined the concept of a musical feedback system designed for stationary bicycles with VR interactivity [28]. In terms of sensors, the system utilizes a 3D accelerometer and gyroscope sensor, M5Stack Core2 which is attached to the thigh of the users. Sensor data is sent via OSC protocol to a JUCE application where thigh rotation velocity is calculated. This application adjusts the tempo of a pre-imported song according to the pace of the cycling. It also connects via OSC to a Unity application called PedaleoVR, which renders the VR graphics of a rabbit running in a 3D environment, which the user must follow as they cycle. A small pilot test was conducted in which participants answered the Presence Questionnaire as well as other questions regarding motivation and session duration. Results were generally promising, although further testing is needed.

2.4.5 D-Jogger

Finally, D-Jogger is an adaptive music player that aims to align movement and music, developed by Moens et. al. [2]. It takes into account gait period (which is related to tempo) and footfall (which is related to phase). In order to do so, it applies a dynamic Kuramoto model, and considers the walker and the music adaptive phase oscillators that must be synchronised. It continuously adapts the music accordingly by slowing down or speeding up the playback as needed. Whenever a song is close

to ending, a different song with a tempo that most closely resembles the walking cycle of the user is queued up from a database, and starts playing only when the desired phase is reached. This strategy seemed extremely successful in terms of maintaining music and motion synchronisation. The system has been proven to increase motivation of runners. It is also useful in the context of Parkinson's disease rehabilitation, by increasing the predictability of steps and therefore reducing risks associated with falling.

A variety of hardware setups were used for different tests. In some cases, a Wii motion plus controller was attached to the participants' ankle, and sent the data wirelessly to a PC. In another instance, a portable version was devised by utilizing Samsung Galaxy Y smartphone which ran the software locally and was attached to a belt in the participant's hips. The most accurate readings were obtained by attaching two iPods, one to each of the user's ankles, and sending sensor data wirelessly to a PC a rate of 100 Hz.

Chapter 3

Materials and methods

This chapter delves into the procedures that were followed in order to carry out this study. Firstly, the profile of the participants who took part in the usability test will be discussed. Secondly, the materials that were utilized will be listed, both in terms of hardware and software. Finally, the main section will serve as a deep dive into the methodology of the project, both in terms of the design philosophy of the musical feedback systems and the experimental design of the test.

3.1 Participants

A total of 9 participants completed the usability test (4 women, 5 men). Their ages ranged from 22 to 31 (average = 25.3, SD = 2.7). Participants responded to a questionnaire about their fitness and music listening habits before they took part in the study.

3.2 Materials

This project consists of two parts: the development of musical feedback systems and the corresponding usability test. As such, this section is also divided into software development and testing equipment.

3.2.1 Software development

All of the interactive software was developed using Unity version 2021.3.24f1, which is a Long Term Support version of the editor that was released on April 27th 2023 [29]. Despite it being a game engine, it is actually a very versatile software development platform. This is in no small part thanks to its vast and enthusiastic community, which continuously pushes the limits of the engine. As a result, it seemed like a good match for the task at hand. Furthermore, its cross-platform compatibility, being able to easily export projects to PC, Android, and more, was truly advantageous.

Some Unity packages created by users were crucial in the implementation of certain aspects of the applications. OscJack by Keijiro allows for OSC connectivity between the Unity engine and external devices [30]. Native File Picker by Yasirkula was necessary in order to import audio files into the app using the file explorer [31]. Finally, UniBpmAnalyzer by WestHillApps was used to obtain the BPM of imported songs, allowing for parameter adjustments based on tempo [32].

For the cooperative versions of the software, in which smartphones connect to a PC host via OSC protocol, the Sensors2OSC app was used [33]. It is an open source Android app that can send any sensor data from a smart device to a host, just by specifying its IP address and UDP port. It was developed by Thomas Mayer and Antonio Deusany de Carvalho Junior. Nonetheless, any other app that accomplishes a similar function would also be compatible with the musical feedback system.

In terms of audio, music loops were produced using Ableton Live 10 [34] as a Digital Audio Workstation, as well as the following virtual instruments: Ample Bass P Lite II [35], City Piano [36], Addictive Drums 2 [37] and Komplete Kontrol [38]. Freesound audio files by YellowTree [39], atomwrath [40], Seidhepriest [41], Logiconomist [42] and sandyrb [43] were used for the orientation-based sampler. Icons by Freepik were used for the user interface [44, 45].

The development was done on an ASUS Zenbook 14 UX431FL-AM049T, with an

Intel Core i7-10510U CPU, 16 GB of RAM and an Nvidia MX250 GPU. It was originally released in 2019 and has a Windows 10 OS [46].

Two Android smartphones were used for testing the applications during development: LG G8s ThinQ and Google Pixel 7a. The LG G8s ThinQ was originally released in 2019 and was updated to an Android 12 OS. It has a Qualcomm SM8150 Snapdragon 855 chipset, an octa-core CPU (1x2.84 GHz Kryo 485 & 3x2.42 GHz Kryo 485 & 4x1.78 GHz Kryo 485), 6 GB of RAM and an Adreno 640 GPU [47].

The Google Pixel 7a was launched in 2023 and features an Android 14 OS. It has Google Tensor G2 chipset, octa-core CPU (2x2.85 GHz Cortex-X1 & 2x2.35 GHz Cortex-A78 & 4x1.80 GHz Cortex-A55), 8 GB of LPDDR5 RAM and a Mali-G710 MP7 GPU [48].

3.2.2 Testing equipment

During the test, participants wore a cell phone armband, which enabled the tracking of their movements through the smartphone's movement sensors. The smartphones used for the experiment were the same ones as during the development phase, LG G8s ThinQ and Google Pixel 7a. Music was played through an Ultimate Ears UE ROLL 2 Bluetooth speaker. A fitness resistance band was used for the bicep curl exercise.

3.3 Methods

Section 3.3.1 presents the design of three different musical feedback systems: "Dynamic loop intensity based on accelerometer fluctuation", "Audio effect modulation through a movement counter" and "Orientation-based sampler through machine learning classification", as well as the collaborative versions of the first two software applications. Section 3.3.2 delves into the experimental design when it comes to evaluating the effects of the second musical feedback system.

3.3.1 Interface Implementation

In order to achieve an state of musical agency while exercising, several interactive applications were developed, both for PC and Android smartphones. These will be referred to as musical feedback systems, or MFS for short. The GitHub repositories containing the Unity Projects for the software applications can be found in Appendix A.

For all of the developed software, movement is measured using the accelerometer readings from the smartphone. It is important to note that accelerometers in smartphones do not simply measure linear acceleration, but rather detect phone orientation. They take into account, not only movement, but also gravity, meaning that even when the phone is completely still, it will sometimes show $\pm 9.8m/s^2$ on some axes (depending on the orientation). This was taken into consideration when designing all applications, since instead of focusing on the specific values of the accelerometer, movement is measured by considering how these values fluctuate. Therefore, this quirk should not affect the reliability of the developed software.

Dynamic loop intensity based on accelerometer fluctuation

The first MFS developed is based on the idea of musical loops that get increasingly more energetic, rhythmically complex and dense as movement increases. Four levels of density were established, named "still", "sparse", "medium" and "dense". There are four instruments playing simultaneously at any given time: drums, piano, bass and lead synthesizer, each one coming from an independent audio source in the Unity Engine. This allows for a certain instrument to change its density level separately from the rest, by changing the audio clip of its corresponding audio source. The movement on the X, Y and Z axes is mapped to the piano, bass and lead synth tracks respectively. Drums take into account the average of all three axes.

Since it has been established that high values in the readings of the accelerometer do not equate to fast movements, there was a necessity to be design a method to calculate the fluctuation of the values. When a smartphone is shaken vigorously, the

values of the accelerometer will vary rapidly and the range of values obtained will be wide. On the other hand, if it's barely moving, the range of values will be narrow. As a result, a good measurement of movement would be the standard deviation of accelerometer values. This philosophy was implemented in two different ways, which will be referred to as "long term" and "short term".

Long term standard deviation takes into account the movement that occurs during the duration of a complete loop (which, in this particular case, is 8 seconds). As the audio clips begin to play, the values given by the accelerometer for each coordinate are each stored on a list. When the audio clip is close to ending (a 500 ms margin was established), the average and the standard deviation values for each coordinate are calculated. These values are categorized into one of the four density levels depending on the range they fall in. The ranges of values standard deviation values assigned to each level were chosen empirically and can be seen in table 1, along with their corresponding audio clips.

Table 1: Criteria for the selection of each of the possible music loops.

Variable	<0.3	0.3-0.9	0.9-1.5	>1.5
Long Term SD X	Still Piano	Sparse Piano	Medium Piano	Dense Piano
Long Term SD Y	Still Bass	Sparse Bass	Medium Bass	Dense Bass
Long Term SD Z	Still Synth	Sparse Synth	Medium Synth	Dense Synth
Average LT SD	Still Drums	Sparse Drums	Medium Drums	Dense Drums

Short term standard deviation was implemented so that the system felt more responsive, as 8 seconds is quite a long wait before noticing the changes that your movement is producing on the music. It is used to change the volume levels of each instrument in the mixer dynamically depending on movement, but it could easily be mapped to different audio effects present in the Unity mixer.

Short term standard deviation uses a sliding window approach. For each of the three coordinates of the accelerometer, the average and standard deviation of the most recent values are calculated. As new values are added to the list, the oldest values are erased from it, maintaining a constant window size. The window size

can be changed using a slider in the user interface. A bigger window means that the standard deviation grows at a slower pace, but it will also take more time to decrease if movement is reduced. On the other hand, a small window size achieves the opposite, sharp rises and sharp drops, which could be considered more responsive, but also less forgiving for the user.

In terms of the code structure, three main scripts should be highlighted, these being *UpdateValues.cs*, *AudioManager.cs* and *FluctuationAnalyzer.cs*. In *UpdateValues.cs*, the accelerometer values are obtained and the UI is updated. *FluctuationAnalyzer.cs* is in charge of all calculations related to the standard deviation of the values of each axis, as well as the average standard deviation, both in the short and long term. Finally, *AudioManager.cs* does the heavy lifting in terms of changing the musical loops audio files and mixer levels according to the calculated fluctuation. In figure 1 a flowchart details the interactions between these scripts.

Figure 1: Flowchart representing the structure of the dynamic loop intensity based on accelerometer fluctuation app

The user interface for the Android application can be seen in figure 2. It features

three different data boxes: current accelerometer values, short term standard deviation and long term standard deviation. Below, there is a checkbox to activate dynamic mixer levels, in which case short term fluctuation will be used to adjust the volume of each instrument in the mix. Finally, at the bottom there is the play/stop button.

Figure 2: User interface for the Dynamic loop intensity based on accelerometer fluctuation app.

Audio effect modulation through a movement counter

Due to the iterative prototyping strategy that was followed for the duration of this project, the second musical feedback system that was created was intended to correct some possible criticisms of the first iteration. One of the most glaring ones was that it could only work with custom made music loops, which offer little variety and might not be to everyone's taste. As a result, for this new application one of the main goals was to be able to give the user freedom to import any song of their liking. This greatly increases the longevity of the system.

The interactivity comes from applying different audio effects to the chosen songs, which evolve according to the user's performance. The Unity Engine comes with an in-built audio mixer that offers a variety of audio effects which can be tinkered with through code. It was decided that distortion and a low-pass filter would be the best fit for the task at hand. When the selected song starts playing, the distortion level is high, and the cutoff frequency of the filter is low, resulting in a harsh and muffled output. As the user begins to move, these parameters react in accordance, making the song sound clearer as a reward for their effort.

Another aspect of the first prototype that could be improved upon is the way that movement is measured. Rewarding sharp fluctuations of the accelerometer values on all axes means that the optimal way of maximizing all variables is, essentially, to shake the smartphone as fast as possible. This could work for certain types of exercise, specially aerobic, but not so well for others. Consequently, a more refined way of tracking user movement was devised.

For this musical feedback system, user movements are being tracked with a zero-crossing detector method. Basically, every time any of the accelerometer coordinates changes its sign, it is counted as a movement. However, it was quickly noted that this lead to some false readings, since this even the slightest movement could trigger the movement counter. The system was oversensitive, and to correct this issue, two thresholds were created.

First, an acceleration threshold, making sure that the difference between the current and previous accelerometer value is significant. Secondly, a delay threshold, meaning that a certain amount of time needs to pass since the latest movement before a new one is counted. With these two thresholds, only significant movements are taken into account. By default, the acceleration threshold was set to 3 m/s^2 , and the delay threshold was set to 300 ms. These values were obtained empirically, and depending on the type of exercise, may not be optimal. As a result, a calibration menu was added, which users can access through a dropdown menu. This allows them to test the current values and modify them as needed using sliders.

Once the accelerometer values were being used effectively to detect significant movements, there was need to map these motions to the sound effects that would be applied to the song chosen by the user. An intuitive way to measure performance with a movement counter such as this would be by considering the pace of the user, meaning the amount of significant movements per time unit. Consequently, a recurring timer was added, meaning, a timer that resets as soon as it ends.

Every time the timer ends, the number of significant movements performed by the user are compared to an established target. In order to choose values for these two variables, the timer and the target, a standard pop song with a tempo of 120 BPM and a 4/4 time signature was used as a reference. The default duration of the timer is 4 seconds, which is equivalent to two measures of the song. It is also half as long as the audio loops of the first MFS, making it more responsive. Considering we tend to move to the beat of the music, the movement target was set to 8, meaning for the maximum possible score is obtained when 8 movements are completed within 4 seconds.

Using linear interpolation, user performance is mapped to the sound effect parameters mentioned previously: distortion level and cutoff frequency of the low-pass filter. Distortion level ranges from 0 to 1, but the maximum distortion was established at 0.5 in order for the song to remain recognisable and not too unpleasant. Likewise, the lowest cutoff frequency for the filter was set to 100 Hz. To match the way in which the human ear perceives frequency changes, the cutoff frequency grows logarithmically as the movement counter increases.

Later in the development process, an option to adjust the time window depending on the imported song's tempo was added. The user can activate this by touching a checkbox above the play button. Tempo detection was achieved thanks to the `UniBpmAnalyzer` package by WestHillApps [32]. As mentioned before, the default 4 second time window was calculated by taking the duration of two measures of a 120 BPM song in 4/4 time signature. When this option is activated, following the same logic, the time window to perform the target number of significant movements will be two measures of a song of the detected tempo (assuming once again 4/4 time

signature).

However, songs with extreme tempos might cause the time window to be either too short or too long. As such, a range was established between a minimum of 60 BPM, which leads to an 8 second time window, and a maximum of 160 BPM, which leads to a 3 second time window. Any tempo below 60 BPM will be multiplied by 2, and any tempo above 160 BPM will be divided by 2, until they resulting tempo is within the range. The range of tempo values was chosen based on a study by C. Stevens et. al. which looks at preferred tempos for bodily movement [19]. Based on this, it could be expected that for extremely slow tempi, users will move at double time, while for extremely fast tempi, users will move at half time.

When it comes to the structure of the code, there are three main scripts that constitute the app. These are *Counter.cs*, *AudioFXManager.cs* and *FilePicker.cs*. *Counter.cs*, as its name implies, is where accelerometer values are acquired and processed in order to count the significant movements. In the script *AudioFXManager.cs*, the parameters of the audio effects are updated every time the looping timer ends. *FilePicker.cs* is a script used to import songs in any audio format into the app, and belongs to the `NativeFilePicker` package, but was modified so that if tempo detection is active, a call to the *TempoDetection.cs* script will be done in order to recalculate the duration of the timer. In figure 3 a flowchart shows the specific interactions between these scripts.

Figure 3: Flowchart representing the structure of the audio effect modulation through a movement counter app

Finally, figure 4 shows the user interface for the Android app. On the left hand side, the "Calibrate" screen is displayed. From top to bottom, it features the dropdown menu to switch between scenes, and below, there are three sliders to adjust important parameters. "Minimum Accel" allows for changes in the acceleration threshold, while "Delay" adjusts the delay threshold. Finally, the target movements per time window can be adjusted. Below there is a counter that will increase every time a significant movement is detected with the current settings. Moreover, the background will switch colors between red and blue with every movement. This allows the user to perceive whether their movements are being recognised even if they are not looking directly at the screen as the smartphone armband will usually be attached to one of their limbs. The counter can be reset to 0 with the button at the bottom.

On the right, the main scene is displayed, containing the musical feedback system. Below the drop down menu there is an "Open file" button which, if pressed, will bring up the file explorer to import an audio file. Below, there is a data box with the current accelerometer values. The large number in the center of the screen is the movement counter, which resets automatically whenever a time window ends. Underneath there is another data box, showing the current distortion level and cutoff frequency, as well as the name of the imported file. Below, a checkbox for tempo detection can be seen. If active, it will show the tempo of the current song as well as the duration of the corresponding time window. Finally, at the bottom, the play/stop button can be found.

Figure 4: User interface for the Audio effect modulation through a movement counter app.

Orientation-based sampler through machine learning classification

Both of the previously mentioned MFS allow the user to interact with a series of audio clips, either by affecting which audio loops are played or by modifying

certain parameters of the audio effects that are applied. However, none of them give immediate feedback but rather reward or penalize the user in accordance to their performance within a small time window. Consequently, there was an opportunity to design an experience that was more responsive and more akin to the act of playing an actual musical instrument. This could be achieved in the form of a sampler, similar to the one described in the Sound Control article [26].

In this case, samples will be triggered depending on the orientation and tilt of the smartphone. The app allows the user to define up to 5 positions that are relevant for the exercise they will be performing. Each position has been assigned a different audio file, and positions are defined according to the values of the three axes of the accelerometer. By implementing a custom K-NN algorithm, the current orientation of the smartphone will be classified into the class of one of the positions defined by the user, triggering the corresponding audio clip. This K-NN algorithm uses euclidean distance and a K of 5.

Upon opening the application, the user is presented with the "Define Positions" scene. This screen consists of five buttons, labeled as positions 1-5. Pressing one of these buttons initiates a 3 second countdown, and during this time the user shall assume a position that is part of the exercise they will be performing. After the countdown ends, 20 accelerometer readings corresponding to said position are stored in a list. The process can be repeated for up to 5 positions that are relevant for the movements that the user will be performing.

Through the dropdown menu, the user can exit the "Define Positions" scene and access the main scene. Upon doing so, whichever lists have been filled with accelerometer values are used as training data. A class called "Data Point" was created, which consists of a `Vector3` variable (accelerometer coordinates) and an integer which indicates which position said vector belongs to. In the "Update" function of the script, which is executed every frame, the distance between current accelerator values and the training data is calculated and the current position is classified. Whenever the classification changes, a different audio clip is triggered.

The structure of the code is composed of mainly of three scripts, *DefinePositions.cs*, *KNNClassifier.cs* and *KNNSampler.cs*. As its name implies, *DefinePositions.cs* is the script in the initial scene that allows users to specify the different postures that will trigger the sounds. In the main scene, *KNNClassifier.cs* is in charge of turning this information into data points, and comparing new accelerometer inputs to the training data in order to classify the current position. Finally, *KNNSampler.cs* plays the corresponding audio clip and updates the UI according to the classification. Figure 5 showcases a flowchart that gives some more insight into the design of the project.

Figure 5: Flowchart representing the structure of the orientation-based sampler through machine learning classification app

The user interface for the software application can be seen in figure 6. On the left, the "Define Positions" screen is shown. Below the dropdown menu to switch between

scenes, the five buttons to store each of the five positions can be seen. Underneath each button there is a small message that describes the current state of the button. The first two show "Position Stored", while the third one is currently in middle of the countdown that occurs before storing a new position. Finally, the last two positions are currently empty.

On the right hand side, the main scene, containing the musical feedback system, can be seen. It displays the current accelerometer values in a data box. Underneath, the group in which the current position has been classified can be seen, in this case, position number 3. Similarly to the calibration screen of the previous app, the background of this scene will change colors whenever a new position is detected. Finally, at the bottom, icons showing a grand piano and a drum kit can be seen, which allow the user to toggle between different audio samples.

Figure 6: User interface for the Orientation-based sampler through machine learning classification app.

Cooperative versions using OSC

An aspect of Jymmin that seemed quite remarkable is how it could create a sense of group belonging when several people experienced it together. As a result, an effort was made to offer a similar cooperative experience by modifying the software developed for this study. Specifically, collaborative versions were developed based on the first two musical feedback systems mentioned in this document.

Cooperative versions can be run locally on a PC, and accelerometer data coming from one or more smartphones is sent via OSC protocol. In order to achieve this, the OSCJack Unity package was a fundamental tool. Namely, the script `EventReceiver.cs` allowed for this software to be developed, which can be added to a game object in the editor. After specifying a UDP Port, host IP address, OSC address and data type, any method from any script can be assigned to it so that it is called every time a new OSC packet is received, using the content of said packet as input variables if the data types are compatible.

The default values in the for connection purposes are as follows. The UDP Port is set as 8000 for the first player, and increases by one for each additional player (e.g., the second player would use port 8001 and so on). IP address is permanently set to localhost and therefore would not ever need to be changed on the PC, although it must be specified on whichever smartphone app is being used to send OSC data. OSC address is the same for all participants, `/accelerometer`. Finally, data type will always be `Vector3`, as this is the format used for accelerometer values.

For testing purposes, the app `Sensors2OSC` was used to send accelerometer data from a smartphone to the host. This is an open source app for Android that can send any sensor values via OSC and therefore fulfilled this purpose perfectly. Nonetheless, any device that is capable of sending accelerometer readings via OSC should be able to connect to the host, regardless of operating system or which app is being used, as long as the UDP port, IP address and OSC address are indicated adequately.

First, a cooperative version of the "dynamic loop intensity based on accelerometer fluctuation" musical feedback system was designed. In this case, up to four

participants can take part in the activity, with each one being assigned a different instrument (bass, piano, synth or drums) depending on the UDP port they choose (8000 to 8003 respectively). Contrary to the design of the individual app, this time instruments are not mapped to specific accelerometer axes. Instead, each participant aims to increase the intensity of the loops of their respective instruments by incrementing the average long term standard deviation of accelerometer values. In other words, every instrument is mapped in the same way that drums were in the individual app, only this time a different person is in charge of each instrument.

Secondly, a cooperative version of the second MFS app, "Audio effect modulation through a movement counter", was developed. In this instance, up to two players can participate. The first participant will connect using UDP port 8000, and will be in charge of reducing distortion levels, while the second participant can connect using UDP port 8001 in order to attempt to push the cutoff frequency of the low-pass filter towards the higher frequencies. The movements of each of the participants are taken into account independently, using two separate movement counters such as the one described in the section pertaining to this musical feedback system app.

A cooperative version of the third musical feedback system "Orientation-based sampler through machine learning classification" wasn't deemed necessary. This is due to the fact that, in this case, each user could simply select audio samples belonging to different musical instruments and, by exercising together recreate the collaborative feeling of playing in a band.

3.3.2 Evaluation

When it came to evaluating the developed software, it was decided that the second app, which consists of audio effect modulation mapped to a movement counter, would be the best option, as it is the most customizable out of the three. Each participant was asked to choose a song of their liking, specifically one that they found motivating in the context of physical exercise. The experiment consisted of two different exercises: jumping jacks and bicep curls.

Jumping jacks are an aerobic exercise where you jump to spread your legs apart while raising your arms overhead, then jump again to return to the starting position with feet together and arms at your sides. A bicep curl is an anaerobic exercise that targets the biceps muscles. It involves lifting a weight (or in this case, stretching a resistance band) by bending the elbow and bringing the weight towards the shoulder while keeping the upper arm stationary.

Subjects were asked to perform these exercises twice, under two different conditions. Under the first condition, their song of choice would play normally in the background. Under the second condition, the song would be played through the musical feedback system app, which would apply distortion and a low pass filter to the audio depending on the pace of their movement.

Exercise repetitions and duration were self-regulated by subjects. They were allowed to stop at any moment, be it due to boredom or exhaustion, so long as their reasoning for stopping would remain consistent for the duration of the experiment. Instructions were given to participants through a consent form which included information in terms of the procedures, risks and benefits, confidentiality, and more. This document can be found in Appendix B.

Some measures were taken in order to reduce biases in regard to the exhaustion level of each participant under each condition. First, in order for subjects to recover, they were allowed to rest for around 2 minutes after each exercise, with a longer break of around 7 minutes between each half of the experiment. The order of each condition was alternated between participants, meaning half of them started exercising with static background music, while the other half were first presented with the MFS app. In the case of the bicep curls, a different arm was used for each half of the experiment, with the starting arm being chosen at random to minimize the bias towards a dominant arm.

For each participant, note was taken on the number of repetitions of each exercise as well as their time. They were also given a two-part questionnaire, which they filled after each half of the test. They were asked to rate their level of exhaustion

and their enjoyment of the workout on a Likert scale from 1 to 5 for each segment of the experiment. In the case of the musical feedback system segment, they were also asked to rate the intuitiveness of the app, meaning their perceived understanding of the mapping of their movement. Some general profile questions were also asked relating to age, gender, fitness habits and music consumption.

Chapter 4

Results

In this chapter, the results of the pilot test for the "Audio effect modulation through a movement counter" app will be presented. First, the profile of the participants will be discussed, outlining the results of the preliminary questionnaire they filled in. Subsequently, the results of the usability test will be shown. The two main quantitative metrics to measure physical performance were repetitions, meaning the number of times a specific exercise was completed, and workout duration. Pace can be calculated by dividing the number of repetitions a participant completed by the time they took to do so, therefore obtaining repetitions per second. Finally, the results of the qualitative test will be presented, which include perceived exhaustion, enjoyment and system intuitiveness as metrics.

4.1 Participant Demographics

Before completing the test, some questions were asked regarding the fitness and music listening habits of the subjects. First, they were asked how often they engage in physical activity on a weekly basis. Only one participant declared that they never exercise. Out of the remaining 8, the answers were overall evenly distributed from 1 to 5 or more workout sessions during a typical week. These sessions tend to be on the longer side, with half of them lasting between 31 and 60 minutes, and the other half being over an hour in length.

When it comes to the way they engage with music, most subjects seem to be avid listeners. A total of 4 participants declared that they listen to music between 2 and 4 hours a day, 3 of them do so around 1 to 2 hours a day, and the remaining 2 spend between 30 minutes to an hour daily listening to music. Lastly, subjects were asked whether they play an instrument or engage in music performance and composition. The answers was affirmative for 8 out of the 9 participants.

4.2 Aerobic exercise: jumping jacks

Figure 7 shows the number of jumping jack repetitions each of the nine participants did under each condition. Passive listening, meaning static background music is shown in blue, while musical agency, which indicates that the musical feedback system was active, is shown in red. This will be the case for every graph in this document.

Figure 7: Jumping jacks repetitions for each of the nine participants under each condition.

Figure 8 shows box plots for jumping jacks repetitions under each condition. Note that due to participant number 7 reaching a mark above 200 repetitions, it is therefore considered an outlier and is not shown in the graph for readability purposes.

Figure 8: Box plot of jumping jacks repetitions under each condition.

Next, figure 9 displays the workout duration for jumping jacks under each of the two conditions.

Figure 9: Jumping jacks workout duration for each of the nine participants under each condition.

In figure 10 the duration of the jumping jacks series under passive listening and musical agency is shown in the form of a box plot. It can be seen that every single statistical measure is higher under musical agency.

Figure 10: Box plot of jumping jacks workout duration under each condition.

No statistical significance was found in terms of jumping jack pace when comparing passive listening to musical agency. The p-value obtained was 0.393.

4.3 Anaerobic exercise: bicep curls

The second exercise that participants executed were bicep curls. As it was the case with jumping jacks, both repetitions and workout duration were measured under both conditions: static background music and active musical feedback. Figure 11 shows the repetitions completed by each participant under each condition.

Figure 11: Bicep curls repetitions for each of the nine participants under each condition.

In figure 12 the performance of participants in regard to bicep curl repetitions in each half of the test is displayed in the form of a box plot. In this case, the upper quartile is the only measure in which passive listening surpasses musical agency.

Figure 12: Box plot of bicep curl repetitions under each condition.

Next, graphs related to the duration of the bicep curl workout sessions will be shown. In figure 13 the time each participant spent performing bicep curls under each condition is displayed as a histogram.

Figure 13: Bicep curls workout duration for each of the nine participants under each condition.

Finally, the duration of the bicep curl series under each condition of the experiment is shown in figure 14 as a box plot. Once again, performance under the musical agency condition surpasses passive listening in terms of statistical measures.

Figure 14: Box plot of bicep curls workout duration under each condition

As it happened with aerobic exercise, no statistical significance was found in terms of bicep curl pace when comparing passive listening to musical agency. The resulting p-value of the t-test was 0.148.

4.4 General overview and qualitative evaluation

The average performance for each type of exercise (jumping jacks and bicep curls) under both conditions (background music and musical feedback system) can be found in table 2. Every single average is higher under musical agency, although variability also seems to increase, as shown by the higher standard deviation values.

Table 2: Average repetitions and time for jumping jacks and bicep curls under the conditions "Background Music" (BM) and "Musical Feedback System" (MFS).

JJ Reps (BM)	JJ Time (BM)	JJ Reps (MFS)	JJ Time (MFS)
58.4 ± 29.9	01 : 03 ± 00 : 33	83.8 ± 53.9	01 : 28 ± 00 : 48
BC Reps (BM)	BC Time (BM)	BC Reps (MFS)	BC Time (MFS)
36.4 ± 13.9	00 : 50 ± 00 : 13	41.4 ± 15.0	00 : 57 ± 00 : 15

The significance of the results in terms of performance, measured in repetitions and workout duration was examined through a one-tailed paired t-test. The resulting p-values can be seen in table 3. For this study, the threshold of statistical significance will be 0.05. With this value in mind, it could be argued that the improvement in terms of bicep curls repetitions and series duration, as well as jumping jacks series duration are all significant.

Table 3: T Test results for jumping jacks and bicep curls in terms of repetitions and time.

Exercise	P-value (Repetitions)	P-value (Time)
Jumping jacks	0.072	0.048
Bicep curls	0.030	0.056

At the end of each half of the experiment, participants were given a qualitative questionnaire in which they were asked to rate their enjoyment and perceived exhaustion under each condition. The survey used a Likert scale ranging from 1 to 5. The averages and t-test results can be seen on table 4. With the aforementioned threshold of 0.05, there doesn't seem to be a statistical significance in terms of perceived level of exertion. Nonetheless, the reported increase in level of enjoyment when utilizing the musical feedback system does seem significant.

Table 4: T Test results for jumping jacks and bicep curls in terms of repetitions and time.

Variable	Background Music	Musical Feedback System	P-value
Exhaustion	3.1 ± 0.8	3.2 ± 1.1	0.341
Enjoyment	2.9 ± 0.9	3.5 ± 1.3	0.025

Furthermore, the questionnaire also included a question regarding the intuitiveness of the musical feedback system in terms of how motion affects the audio. Specifically, the prompt was: "The system is intuitive. I understood the general idea of how it works and how my movement is mapped". The resulting average score was 3.1 ± 1.1 .

Chapter 5

Discussion

In this chapter, the results from the pilot test will be examined. Afterwards, the limitations of this study will be brought up and discussed. Next, the possible avenues for future work that could be done in order to expand this research will be explored. Finally, the conclusions that have been derived from this project will be highlighted.

5.1 Discussion

The quantitative portion of the test takes into account workout performance of participants by measuring the number of repetitions and workout duration for each exercise and under each condition. In the vast majority of cases, both variables were higher under a state of musical agency. Taking a p-value of 0.05 as a threshold for statistical significance, the results of the t-test regarding performance are quite positive. The number of bicep curl repetitions and the duration of jumping jacks workout duration are both under the threshold, with bicep curl workout duration just barely surpassing it. The worst result would be the number of jumping jack repetitions, with a p-value of 0.072, which isn't too high, but also not ideal.

Exercising pace, meaning repetitions per second, was also calculated for each participant under each condition. However, results point toward a lack of statistical significance for both aerobic and anaerobic exercises. Since the same song was play-

ing under both conditions, it could be argued that most participants maintained a similar pace since it feels more natural to exercise to the tempo of the song.

One of the most unambiguous results related to the experiment is that participants generally found the workout session with musical agency more satisfying than with static background music. Out of the 9 subjects, 6 claimed that the musical feedback system made the experience more enjoyable, and with a p-value of 0.025, this seems certainly significant. It is a very positive figure despite the small sample size, and it alone is a compelling reason to continue expanding the research in this field.

In terms of perceived exertion felt by participants, musical agency seems to have little to no effect. This is illustrated by the high p-value of 0.341 which was obtained after the t-testing the subject's answers. Therefore, there doesn't seem to be statistical significance that can support a reduced feeling of exhaustion under a state of musical agency. This is in line with the results of other musical feedback systems, such as D-Jogger [2], and one of the most recent Jymmin-related publications [4], although it contradicts the findings of the original Jymmin article [3].

When it comes to the intuitiveness of the tested system, it scored an average of 3.1 ± 1.1 out of 5. This figure is almost in the middle of the scale, meaning that participants were mostly neutral to this statement and did not have very strong opinions on the matter. This seems reasonable, as no concrete explanation of how the app works was given to them before the test. Therefore, the fact that they could somewhat describe its inner workings just by blindly using it can be seen as a positive. However, this score is certainly improvable. A possible way to do so would be to reduce both the time window and target repetitions of the system in an attempt to make it feel more responsive, but this comes with its own set of drawbacks.

5.1.1 Limitations

There are a few shortcomings that should be underlined in relation to this study. First, even though three different musical feedback systems were developed (plus

cooperative versions for two of them), only one was ever tested. There are many reasons for this, mainly related to time constraints, as there was an overlap between some of the development and testing time. Moreover, the sessions of a test that is physically demanding such as this one should be kept short. Extending the session's duration in order to test more than one system could lead to accumulated fatigue, impacting performance and mood.

Secondly, the sample size of the pilot test was rather small with only 9 participants. Thus, outliers could potentially have a significant impact on the overall results. Consequently, it seems rash to uphold the results of this study as conclusive. Rather, a more prudent goal was set to examine what the trends and findings of more prominent publications in the field are and attempt to replicate their results to some extent.

The experiment design itself could be considered flawed by some. Mainly, in regards to the notion that workout duration being self-regulated by participants could introduce some subjectivity in terms of their output. This is a reasonable point. However, when measuring physical endurance, it will always be up to the subject to decide when to stop, and asking them to push themselves to their absolute limit seems unnecessarily risky and could lead to discomfort, if not worse. Moreover, the qualitative questionnaire given to participants could have been more in depth, focusing on specific emotions that they felt under each condition.

Another criticism that could be brought up is whether the benefits of musical feedback systems could be maintained in the long term, or on the contrary, are a consequence of the excitement that comes from experiencing something for the first time. This is a fair inquiry related to all studies in the field. Personally, I was unable to find publications in which participant's workout output is tracked across a longer period of time. In any case, this would be a possible avenue for future work.

5.1.2 Future work

There are two main possible avenues for future work: continuing software development in order to improve the MFS apps and conducting tests that are more in depth and have greater sample sizes.

In terms of software development, there is a possibility of creating a new musical feedback system altogether or improving upon the already developed software. Some interesting inspiration for a brand new and more complex MFS could be taken from projects mentioned in the "State Of The Art" section. For instance, a more active music-making experience could be achieved by implementing something similar to the FMSynth found in Sound Control [26], which leverages three neural networks, allowing the user to control the carrier frequency, harmonicity, and modulation index of FM synthesis.

Some improvements could be made to the already developed musical feedback systems. In terms of the Dynamic Loop Intensity system and the Orientation-based Sampler, the main drawback would be their limited options in terms of audio clips. Therefore, more variety would be welcome in order to expand the longevity of the apps. The Audio Effect Modulation MFS could be improved by allowing the user to import several songs (essentially, workout playlists) instead of one at a time. An approach similar to D-Jogger [2] could be taken, where a expansive database of annotated songs exists and whenever the current song is close to ending, the next one is selected in order to match the tempo of the exercise and facilitate synchronisation.

When it comes to testing, an approach similar to Jymmin could be followed. Jymmin has been extensively tested, with each study looking at different variables such as perceived exertion [3], mood [1], physical endurance [4], divergent thinking [22], sense of group belonging [24], desire to relapse in substance abuse [23], as well as people coming from different backgrounds, such as elderly people or polydrug abusers.

A particularly interesting group would be people diagnosed with Parkinson's disease, as both music and exercise have been proven to be immensely beneficial in terms

of alleviating their symptoms. Studies conducted with musical feedback system D-Jogger focusing on this subset of participants also lead promising results [2].

5.2 Conclusions

This study set out to develop an accessible musical feedback system for exercising, and to analyze its effects in terms of physical performance, perceived sense of exertion, and enjoyment. In the end, three different systems were designed and developed, due to the iterative prototyping strategy that was followed.

The first one was based on musical loops that become increasingly intense and energetic with the fluctuation of accelerometer values on each axis. The second one, which is the one that was tested, allows the user to import whichever song they favor, and applies distortion and a filter that the user must remove by reaching a target number of significant movements within a time window. Finally, the third one is an orientation-based sampler that allows the user to define up to 5 positions and then plays different audio clips by classifying the current orientation of the smartphone into one of those positions through a K-NN algorithm.

Later, cooperative versions of the first and second MFS were developed. These run on a PC, to which several participants send their smartphone's accelerometer data via OSC protocol. The main goal behind these versions of the software is to turn the musical agency workout experience into a bonding activity, with the hopes of creating a feeling of group belonging.

In terms of the results of the test, there are certain inferences that can be made, although, as it was said in the "Limitations" section, due to the small sample size, they should not be taken as decisive. However, the results seem to point towards musical agency being able to increase physical performance, both in terms of number of repetitions and workout duration.

No evidence was found supporting that exercising in a state of musical agency can reduce the perceived level of exhaustion. Neither did the use of a musical feedback system lead to an increase in exercise pace. On the other hand, a majority of

participants found a greater level of enjoyment when receiving musical feedback during their workout.

In conclusion, musical feedback systems for exercising seem to provide a myriad of benefits for their users. These range from increased workout performance without increasing perceived exertion, to greater enjoyment of the activity. While this study in particular was done at a smaller scale, it serves as proof that it is possible to create musical feedback systems that are widely available and accessible, by leveraging the motion sensors in smartphones. As such, it would be immensely valuable to continue expanding the knowledge of this field as we improve the ways in which music making and exercising intertwine.

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Appendix A

GitHub Repositories

The Unity Projects containing all of the code and assets related to the software applications that were developed for this study can be found in the following URLs:

- Musical Feedback Systems: <https://github.com/ogmario/Musical-Feedback-Systems>
- Cooperative Musical Feedback Systems: <https://github.com/ogmario/Cooperative-Musical-Feedback-Systems>

Appendix B

Usability Test Consent Form

Musical Feedback System for Exercising

Usability Test Consent Form

Introduction: You are invited to participate in a usability test of a musical feedback system designed to enhance exercising experiences. Please read this form carefully and feel free to ask any questions before agreeing to participate. During this usability test, you will be asked to interact with a musical feedback system while engaging in various exercise activities. The system will apply different audio effects to a song based on your movements. The goal is to assess how well the system supports and motivates your workout routine.

Procedures: You will be asked to choose a song of your liking as workout music for this activity. First, the song will be played as background music while you exercise. Exercise consists of one set of jumping jacks and one set of bicep curls using an elastic band. These sets can be as long as you desire (or until you feel tired). You may take a minute to rest between these sets. Before the second part of the test, you may take a short break to fill out the first half of the questionnaire. For the second half of the test, the song you chose will be played through the musical feedback system. The physical exercises will be the same as in the first half. For the bicep

curls, use the opposite arm. After the test, you will be asked to provide feedback by filling out the second half of the questionnaire.

Risks and Benefits: There are minimal risks associated with this study, such as potential discomfort during physical activity. The benefits include contributing to the improvement of a novel exercise-enhancing technology and potentially discovering new ways to make exercising more enjoyable.

Confidentiality: Any information collected during this study will remain confidential. Your data will be anonymized and used for research purposes only.

Participation and Withdrawal: Participants can freely withdraw from the test at any time without needing to provide an explanation, and their decision will not impact their relationship with the researchers or the institution.

Consent: I have read and understood the information provided in this consent form. I voluntarily agree to participate in the usability test of the musical feedback system for exercising, understanding that I may withdraw at any time. I consent to the collection and use of data for research purposes.

- Participant's Name:

- Participant's Signature:

- Date:

Researcher's Confirmation: I have explained the nature and purpose of this study to the participant. I confirm that the participant has voluntarily agreed to participate and has received a copy of this consent form.

- Researcher's Name: Mario Ortega García

- Researcher's Signature:

- Date: